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Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) Monitoring Manual

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Purpose

The University of Hull (UoH) has developed a manual to serve as a blueprint for the monitoring of Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS). The initiative was driven by the need for a standardised, practical framework to guide organisations, researchers, and practitioners in the effective evaluation of SuDS performance.

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**Denotes equal contributions*

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Disclaimer:

The specific sensor manufacturer and models identified in this document are provided as examples. Alternative sensors from other manufacturers not listed here are also available. The partners involved in this project do not endorse or recommend any specific manufacturer or model listed within this document, and you should ensure the sensor you choose fits your specific needs prior to installation.

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Why monitor SuDS?

Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) are becoming more common due to growing concerns about surface water management to reduce flood risk, the need to reduce pressure on drainage systems, and the benefits for improving water quality. SuDS often involve multiple stakeholders, such as local and combined authorities, water companies, environmental agencies, highways authorities, and local communities. Gaining support from all these groups requires a strong evidence base that demonstrates the effectiveness of how different SuDS features deliver improved water quality (through bioremediation), reduced flood risk (through water storage and slowing flows) and increased biodiversity and amenity value (through sustainable and place-making design).

Real-time monitoring of SuDS is essential for understanding their performance and providing a robust evidence base for further investment. Instrumenting SuDS features provides valuable data to evaluate their effectiveness as built compared to model designs, identify opportunities for improvement, and adapt future designs. Monitoring supports understanding both small-scale SuDS and larger, community-focused systems, offering insights into their functionality across different environments.

SuDS performance data allows for better ongoing management of existing infrastructure and can inform the design of future interventions to maximise their impact and make investments in water management both better targeted and more valuable. It also helps in modelling water and contaminant behaviour and predicting how SuDS networks will cope with future challenges like climate change and urban growth. Importantly, sharing these data with local communities and other stakeholders helps demonstrate the benefits, efficacy and importance of SuDS in their area. In addition, the increase in monitoring and the availability of hyper-local data can provide significant improvements in flood risk warning and community action to mitigate flood risks.

This manual provides guidance on the design, installation, and maintenance of instruments for monitoring SuDS hydrology, aimed at water companies, local authorities, and researchers invested in measuring the impact of sustainable drainage.

When to monitor SuDS?

Sewer Monitoring

Monitoring SuDS before and after deployment is vital for evidence-based urban water management. Pre-works sewer analysis informs targeted design, while post-implementation evaluations validate performance, ensuring SuDS reduce flood risk, improve water quality and show the benefit of adaptation to climate change. This cyclical process supports adaptive management, enabling refinements to maximise resilience and sustainability in dynamic environments.

Pre-SuDS Installation

Prior to SuDS installation, there needs to be thorough sewer monitoring to record baseline hydrological and environmental parameters. This includes measurement of capacity, flow rates, and water quality of the sewer network to highlight flow pathways, frequency of overflows or surcharging, and pollutant loads. Flow gauges, water quality sensors (turbidity, pH, heavy metals), and CCTV surveys allow these metrics to be recorded. For instance, pre-works data may establish sewer surcharging during trigger storm rainfall events, pointing out areas where SuDS could alleviate pressure. This phase ensures SuDS designs are tailored to address site-specific challenges, such as diverting excess runoff or filtering contaminants, while avoiding unintended consequences for existing infrastructure. Ideally, sewer monitoring should occur for 1 year prior to design to ensure that SuDS are optimised for known flow conditions in a sewer network or at least 1 year prior to SuDS installation for evaluation of post-SuDS impact. The longer the duration of monitoring and the greater number of rainfall events captured are the key controls on maximising the impact of any pre-monitoring data.

Post-SuDS Installation

After SuDS installation, ongoing monitoring compares post-intervention data with pre-works baselines to assess effectiveness. Key metrics include reductions in peak flow rates (indicating slower runoff), improvements in water quality (e.g., lower sediment or nutrient concentrations), and decreased flood incidents. Continuous flow monitoring and sensor networks track real-time performance, while visual inspections evaluate structural integrity and ecological benefits, such as habitat creation. For instance, a SuDS scheme incorporating permeable pavements and rain gardens should demonstrate lower sewer discharge volumes and enhanced pollutant retention. Post-monitoring also identifies maintenance needs, such as silt removal from basins, ensuring long-term functionality. As with pre-SuDS monitoring strategies, monitoring after the installation of SuDS should, ideally, be for at least 1 year in duration.

SuDS Monitoring

Once SuDS are built, ongoing monitoring is essential to ensure they function and perform as designed, providing effective flood mitigation, water quality improvement, and environmental benefits. Post-construction monitoring focuses on assessing the performance of SuDS components, identifying maintenance needs, and ensuring long-term sustainability. Building an extensive database of SuDS performance after construction is essential to improve models, since real-world data of SuDS infrastructure can be used to feed realistic parameters into models and ensure that systems deliver the expected results.

Key Monitoring Objectives

After SuDS are installed, the primary goal is to evaluate their hydrological and environmental performance. This includes measuring water quantity (e.g., runoff volume, flow rates, and infiltration rates) and water quality (e.g., pollutant removal efficiency). Monitoring also assesses ecological benefits, such as habitat creation and biodiversity enhancement, as well as structural integrity to prevent failures.

A combination of tools and methods are used to monitor SuDS. Flow gauges and water level sensors track runoff volumes and flow rates, measuring how SuDS attenuate peak flows during rainfall events. Water quality sensors measure parameters like turbidity, pH, nutrient levels, and heavy metals to evaluate changes in pollutant s. Visual inspections are conducted to check for blockages, sediment buildup, or damage to components like permeable pavements, swales, or retention basins. Ecological surveys can also be performed to monitor vegetation health and wildlife activity, ensuring SuDS contribute to biodiversity.

Monitoring requires continuous data collection, especially after heavy rainfall events, to identify issues like clogging or overflow. Data collected helps prioritise maintenance tasks, such as removing sediment from basins, clearing vegetation from swales, or repairing damaged structures. Long-term monitoring ensures SuDS adapt to changing conditions, such as increased rainfall intensity due to climate change.

Framework for Monitoring

Network Creation

Effective sensing for SuDS installations need to ensure that data is easily accessible to users. To meet this requirement, some sensors store data for manual collection later, however, live data transmission provides significantly better opportunities to make use of the data collected. Importantly, live data allows rapid analysis of system responses to weather events, enables opportunities for data to be backed up on a server, reduces the risk of data loss if a sensor is damaged and enables data to be used for local response. Hence, a live networked system that collects this data is a particularly effective option, with several network types available.

Centralised radio mesh networks

Centralised networks send data to one point, called a "gateway," which transmits it to a server for access. Gateways need a power source and internet connection, either through broadband or cellular networks. For convenience, they are often placed in nearby public buildings, with permission. Mains-powered or battery-operated nodes (with solar panels for recharging) with radio aerials can communicate with the gateway over distances of hundreds of meters, depending on power availability and radio communication conditions. Connectivity issues can occur in busy areas, such as interference from 5G signals or other radio-based devices/systems, which use overlapping frequencies. Centralised networks work best in areas with many sensors, as one internet connection can handle multiple devices.

Example: Davis EnviroMonitor.

Cellular/Satellite Distributed methods

Distributed communication devices do not rely on central nodes to transmit data to a server. Instead, they often use cellular or satellite networks, requiring annual subscription fees for connectivity for each connection point. These networks are ideal for remote areas, widely spaced sensors, or locations with only a few sensors, as they eliminate the need for a central gateway. This makes them cost-effective for smaller setups.

Examples include Metasphere and Dales Land Net (for soil moisture only).

LoRaWAN

LoRaWAN networks offer a middle ground between centralised radio and cellular networks. Using the LoRa (Long Range) signal, they transmit data to a gateway like radio mesh networks but typically provide greater range. Like mesh networks, LoRaWAN requires careful gateway placement, often near power and internet sources. These networks balance cost and performance, making them suitable for many applications.

Example: TEKTELIC Kiwi sensor.

Locating base stations/gateways

As stated above, some networks require a point through which wirelessly transmitted data can be routed onto the internet and to the data server, and the hardware to do this usually needs a reliable power supply and internet connection and is frequently not weather-proof. Due to this it is usually best to site this gateway in a building near the monitored site but finding a building to which monitoring staff can gain easy and convenient access to can be difficult. Private buildings are frequently not suitable for this, and so public buildings such as schools and community centres are potentially preferred options. The advantages of these include:

- **Easy access:** Public Community buildings are frequently open during work hours, and have multiple staff through which access can be negotiated
- **Community engagement:** Central public buildings offer the opportunity to act as both centres for data collection and centres for engagement with the communities into which the monitored SuDS features are to be built.

Weather Station

Weather stations don't directly monitor SuDS but are used to constrain the precipitation and evapotranspiration gains and losses from SuDS systems and are therefore critical for monitoring of the baseline conditions of hydrological systems. Effective SuDS evaluation requires these data to be acquired as close to the SuDS installation as possible to ensure that the impact of localised weather events can be matched to SuDS performance at a hyper-local level.

What to monitor?

- **Precipitation:** Indicates the input into the whole SuDS system
- **Evapotranspiration (ET):** Indicates rate of water lost from the SuDS
- **Temperature:** Used to calculate ET (Also, possibly for assessing the effects of SuDS on urban air temperature)
- **Solar Radiation:** Used to calculate ET
- **Windspeed:** Used to calculate ET
- **Humidity:** Used to calculate ET

Module	Requirements	Comment
Evapotranspiration	Calculation of ET using Penman-Monteith equation or derivative, to accuracy ≤ 0.05 mm/hr	
Windspeed	Accuracy ≤ 0.5 ms ⁻¹ (below 5 ms ⁻¹), 10% (above 5 ms ⁻¹)	
Precipitation (intensity)	Measured as either instantaneous intensity, average intensity over ~15 minutes or total precipitation over ~15 minutes. Approx. accuracy ≤ 0.1 mm ¹	Higher temporal resolution the better to quantify the time lag between rainfall and SuDS system reaction.
Temperature	Accuracy ≤ 0.2 °C	
Solar radiation	Accuracy $\leq 5\%$	

¹ From achievable uncertainty; WMO Guide to instruments and methods:

<https://library.wmo.int/records/item/68695-guide-to-instruments-and-methods-of-observation?offset=5>

Positioning

Care should be taken when siting the weather station to make sure that external influences do not add significant error to the measurements taken. Correct positioning of weather stations is discussed in detail in the World Meteorological Organization Guide to Instruments and Methods. Here, we present a simplified version of the scheme described by the WMO, with a somewhat less stringent specification to allow for practical placement close to SuDS features and/or within secure locations at school/community sites.

Weather stations should be situated on a free-standing pole in an open space, ideally over regularly cut grass (parks and school playing fields great for this), where it is freely exposed to sun, wind and rain. The site should be as flat as possible, avoiding slopes and hollows, and away from tall buildings or trees that could shade or shelter sunlight, wind, temperature or rain gauges. For accurate wind measurement, the distance to any nearby object (trees or buildings) should be no less than 2.5 x the height of the object above station, and ideally more than 5 x the height of the object above the station as shown in the diagram below.

The WMO stipulates that anemometers should be mounted at a height of 10 m, thermometers should be mounted 1.25 - 2 m above the ground, and rain gauges at ground level. However, for practicality, here we suggest mounting all instruments together at around 1.5 - 2 m from the ground, with the anemometer mounted highest, at the top of the post a height ~2m, and the rain gauge mounted lowest. This is advised as a) many weather stations are integrated systems with limited cable lengths between

sensors, and b) to maintain safe working heights. Considerations specific to each sensor include:

- **Temperature-** Should be within a louvred radiation screen, usually standard with commercial weather stations.
- **Wind-** Ideally at the top of the pole to avoid interference from it, but otherwise on a boom at distance $\geq 3 \times$ the diameter of the pole.
- **Rainfall-** Gauges should be protected from excessive wind, either by siting the rain gauge as low as possible and surrounding them with windshields if this is possible.

Note about siting: WMO requirements are formulated to give an accurate measure of the general weather in the area, without interference from local human or natural topography. However, as the purpose of the weather stations discussed here is to measure conditions at and around particular SuDS feature(s), if these features are affected by local topography, it may be sensible to waive some regulations in the interest of situating the weather station close to the features it is meant to monitor. This is especially true for temperature and windspeed, as the effects of shading and shelter likely affect the SuDS feature (i.e. the “error” in readings may actually be representative of conditions at the SuDS). However, care should be taken to make rainfall measurements accurate, as rainfall intercepted by trees and buildings will likely make its way to the ground, and into the SuDS eventually.

Hydrologic Monitoring

Planters

SuDS planters are systems that channel water (usually rainwater) into a tank containing soil and plants with the aim of retaining flow and pollutants. Planters often also include a secondary water reservoir after the soil container, that increases the volume of water held (though doesn't contribute to bioretention of pollutants) before the water is output into the surface water drainage network by restricting the outflow rate. These systems are usually installed as free-standing planters and can be augmented with increased amenity or biodiversity value through the addition of, for example, seating benches or additional wildlife habitats such as insect 'hotels'.

Planters represent an opportunity for easy monitoring of SuDS due to their small size and tightly constrained input and outputs; they can be monitored with just two flow meters and a single soil moisture probe. In addition, if the planter includes a water storage tank, then an additional water depth sensor can be installed in the water retention tank below the planter. The greatest challenge with monitoring planters is the wide range of potential inflow and outflow rates which means that any measurement system must cope with a wide variation in flow rates. In addition, devices that measure very low flow rates usually rely on small diameter pipework which are narrower than most downpipes.

What to monitor:

- **Downpipe flow:** To quantify the input into the planter.
- **Outflow / Drain flow:** To quantify the output from the planter.
- **Soil moisture:** Temporal and depth changes in moisture indicate water storage dynamics.
- **Retention Tank Water Depth (optional):** Storage of water within planter reservoir.
- **Precipitation:** Correlation of rain and water depth/moisture peaks

Considerations:

- **Power considerations for nodes:** Battery/Solar panel combination should have sufficient capacity and input to power the whole system, even over long periods of cloudy weather. Replaceable batteries allow continuous monitoring even in the event of a fault with solar power. Mains power is preferable if it can be facilitated (and planters, due to being located next to buildings, are well suited to this), though this has frequently been found to be difficult.

- **Connectivity with instruments:** Connectivity options should be checked to make sure all equipment can communicate with the central hub. SDI-12 connections have proved successful in our trials, due to being widely available, open, and low power consumption.
- **Overflow system:** To prevent any possible flooding due to blockages of the flow sensor measurement systems, an emergency overflow system is recommended to be installed on a planter setup as a failsafe.
- **Constriction of flow:** Depending on the pipe configuration/ flow meter selected, water will be required to flow in a downsized pipe. Depending on roof area/ pipe the system may experience backflow. Using the [Drain Calculator](#) web app has the most common pipe sizes to allow for confidence in design.

Suggested Requirements:

Module	Requirements
Node	Solar powered with sufficient battery life or directly wired if possible. Connectivity with all below instruments and capacity for 4 connected instruments.
Inflow	Accuracy: for tipping bucket ≤ 10 ml per tip per m^2 of roof area (equivalent to 0.01mm rain); for constant flow meters ≤ 60 ml $minute^{-1}$ per m^2 . Maximum flow capacity estimated from maximum probable rainfall and roof area.
Outflow	As above, but with higher accuracies to capture slower flows leaving the planter. for constant flow meters ≤ 5 ml $minute^{-1}$ per m^2 .
Soil Moisture	Length close to soil depth in the planter. Readings at 10 cm intervals or less
Reservoir Level (Optional)	Accuracy ≤ 0.5 cm
Reservoir Conductivity (Optional)	Accuracy ≤ 0.05 dS/m

This diagram shows the effective measurement ranges for a given rainfall rates falling on different roof areas for a downpipe with a tipping bucket gauge and/or flowmeter specified in the table above.

Example Layouts:

Real-World Example:

Western Primary School, Grimsby

Rain Garden

Highway rain gardens are a practical SuDS solution designed to manage runoff from roads, hardstanding/parking or roofs while also providing opportunities for improving water quality. These features typically include vegetation and soil layers that slow water flow, promote infiltration, and filter out pollutants before the water reaches drainage systems or natural water bodies.

Monitoring for highway rain gardens often focuses on soil moisture levels to understand how effectively the garden retains water and supports plant health. In addition, measuring the depth and conductivity of water in the outfall chamber provides valuable insights into pollutant removal and the overall performance of the system. These metrics help ensure the rain garden is functioning as intended and adapting to varying storm events effectively. Where raingardens are fed by discharge from specific sources such as building roofs, there is also the opportunity to measure inflow from downpipes.

What to monitor:

- **Outflow depth and conductivity:** To quantify the flux through the rain gardens and estimate storage and effects on flood peaks.
- **Outflow Water Quality:** To quantify the pollutant load leaving a rain garden against water quality metrics to show filtering/ bioremediation impact.
- **Soil moisture:** Temporal and depth changes in moisture indicate water storage dynamics.
- **Precipitation:** Correlation of rain and water depth/moisture peaks

Considerations:

- **Power considerations for nodes:** Battery/Solar panel combination should have sufficient capacity and input to power the whole system, even over long periods of cloudy weather. Replaceable batteries allow continuous monitoring even in the event of a fault with solar power. Mains power is preferable if it can be facilitated though this has frequently been found to be difficult.
- **Connectivity with instruments:** Connectivity options should be checked to make sure all equipment can communicate with the central hub. SDI-12 connections have proved successful in our trials, due to being widely available, open, and low power consumption.
- **Installation:** Cables will need to be ran with conduits already installed into the system as when built it can be difficult to feed cables to the right locations safely.

Soil moisture probe(s)/ Output probe may need to be installed into the system if there is a requirement to be situated deeper within the structure.

- **Maintenance:** Water Quality probes may need routine maintenance (weeks/ months) and therefore need to be safe to remove and easy to access.

Suggested Requirements:

Module	Requirements
Node	Solar powered with sufficient battery life or directly wired if possible. Connectivity with all below instruments and capacity for 3 connected instruments.
Chamber Level	Accuracy ≤ 2 mm
Chamber Conductivity	Accuracy ≤ 0.05 dS/m
Water Quality	Turbidity ($\pm 2\%$ or ± 0.1 NTU), Temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$), pH (± 0.1), Dissolved Oxygen (± 0.1 mg/l), Nitrogen/ Phosphorus ($\pm 5\%$), heavy metals ($\pm 5\%$) and Hydrocarbons (low $\mu\text{g/L}$).
Soil Moisture	Length close to soil depth in the rain garden/ crates. Readings at 10 cm intervals or less
Precipitation	Accuracy ≤ 0.2 mm

Example Layout:

Real-World Example:

Broadway, Grimsby

Retention/ Detention Pond

Naming conventions around SuDS ponds that hold water to slow its transport into the drainage network or fluvial systems vary widely. These features can be described as retention or detention ponds or basins and are also known as aqua-greens. The exact functionality and operation of systems varies widely depending on their location and purpose within any water management system. However, the overall operation and monitoring requirements are sufficiently similar for different systems to enable a single monitoring strategy. For simplicity, here we refer to features that can hold water, but which are designed to be predominantly dry as detention basins, and features that are designed to hold water most of the time as retention ponds. This category can include ponds where inflow and outflow are either split or located together, as well as both lined and unlined basins.

As with other SuDS, monitoring should attempt to capture water flow into and out of the system, as well as the related contaminant fluxes. Soil moisture and conductivity measurements in and around the in and around the SuDS feature provide critical data into the movement of water and contaminants through shallow groundwater, especially in unlined ponds. Precipitation data will help to quantify inputs to the SuDS system, as well as the speed at which the above metrics respond to precipitation.

What to monitor:

- **Inflow/ Outflow Depth:** To quantify the flux through the pond and estimate storage and effects on flood peaks.
- **Inflow/ Outflow Conductivity:** To quantify the effect of the pond on water contamination.
- **Inflow/ Outflow Water Quality:** To quantify the pollutant load leaving a pond against water quality metrics to show bioremediation impact.
- **Soil moisture:** Monitoring the infiltration of water into soil and retention of moisture in soil layers (in retention ponds). Multiple soil moisture probes may be required – one in the base of basins, one underneath the lining of a lined pond, and one in “natural” conditions near the pond.
- **Precipitation:** Correlation of rain and water depth/moisture peaks

Considerations:

- **Power considerations for nodes:** Battery/ Solar panel combination should have sufficient capacity and input to power the whole system, even over long periods of

cloudy weather. Replaceable batteries allow continuous monitoring even in the event of a fault with solar power. Mains power is preferable if it can be though this has frequently been found to be difficult.

- **Connectivity with instruments:** Connectivity options should be checked to make sure all equipment can communicate with the central hub. SDI-12 connections have proved successful in our trials, due to being widely available, open, and low power consumption.
- **Installation:** Open spaces need to have probes either hidden or in safe enclosures to minimise vandalism. Suggested placement of probes in headwall structures or within dedicated chamber units.
- **Maintenance:** Water Quality probes may need routine maintenance (weeks/ months) and therefore need to be safe to remove and easy to access.

Suggested Requirements:

Module	Requirements
Node	Solar powered with sufficient battery life, or directly wired if possible. Connectivity with all below instruments and capacity for 4 connected instruments.
Inflow/ Outflow Depth	Accuracy \leq 10 mm, or \leq 1% of depth if inflow depth exceeds 1 m
Inflow/ Outflow Conductivity	Accuracy \leq 0.05 dS/m
Water Quality	Turbidity (\pm 2% or \pm 0.1 NTU), Temperature (\pm 0.1°C), pH (\pm 0.1), Dissolved Oxygen (\pm 0.1 mg/l), Nitrogen/ Phosphorus (\pm 5%), heavy metals (\pm 5%) and Hydrocarbons (low μ g/L).
Soil moisture	Depth chosen to reflect area/ pond type. Readings at 10 cm intervals or less
Precipitation	Accuracy \leq 0.2 mm

Layout:

- A: Node w/ rain gauge
- B: Soil Moisture Sensor
- C: CTD in well behind headwall

Real-World Example:

Wybers Wood

Swale

Wet and dry swales are key features of SuDS, designed to manage stormwater while enhancing water quality and promoting ecological benefits. Though similar in their purpose of conveying and treating runoff, their operation and characteristics differ. Dry swales are typically engineered to remain dry between rainfall events, relying on a permeable base to promote infiltration. Wet swales, on the other hand, are designed to hold water for extended periods, often incorporating a shallow water layer to support wetland vegetation and natural treatment processes.

Both types of swales share a common goal of slowing water flow and capturing pollutants, but their design and function cater to different site conditions. Dry swales are ideal for areas with well-draining soils and focus on reducing runoff through infiltration. Wet swales are better suited to locations with higher water tables or where prolonged water retention is beneficial for pollutant removal or biodiversity.

Effective monitoring of swales should consider their unique characteristics. For dry swales, infiltration rates, soil moisture levels, and sediment accumulation provide insights into performance and maintenance needs. For wet swales, parameters such as water depth, vegetation health, and nutrient or contaminant levels are critical for assessing their function and environmental impact. Additionally, rainfall data helps connect swale performance to storm events, offering a clear picture of how these features respond to varying intensities and durations.

Whether wet or dry, swales are a versatile and valuable component of sustainable drainage, balancing water management with ecological enhancement. Understanding their performance through targeted monitoring ensures they continue to meet both hydrological and environmental objectives effectively.

What to monitor:

- **Inflow/ Outflow:** To quantify the flux through the swale and estimate storage and effects on flood peaks.
- **Inflow/ Outflow conductivity:** To quantify the effect of the swale on water contamination.
- **Inflow/ Outflow Water Quality:** To quantify the pollutant load leaving a swale against water quality metrics to show bioremediation impact.
- **Soil moisture:** Monitoring the infiltration of water into soil and retention of moisture in soil layers
- **Precipitation:** Correlation of rain and water depth/moisture peaks

Considerations:

- **Power considerations for nodes:** Battery/ Solar panel combination should have sufficient capacity and input to power the whole system, even over long periods of cloudy weather. Replaceable batteries allow continuous monitoring even in the event of a fault with solar power. Mains power is preferable if it can be facilitated though this has frequently been found to be difficult.
- **Connectivity with instruments:** Connectivity options should be checked to make sure all equipment can communicate with the central hub. SDI-12 connections have proved successful in our trials, due to being widely available, open, and low power consumption.
- **Installation:** Open spaces need to have probes either hidden or in safe enclosures to minimise vandalism. Suggested placement of probes in headwall structures or within dedicated chamber units.
- **Maintenance:** Water Quality probes may need routine maintenance (weeks/ months) and therefore need to be safe to remove and easy to access.

Suggested Requirements:

Module	Requirements
Node	Solar powered with sufficient battery life, or directly wired if possible. Connectivity with all below instruments and capacity for 4 connected instruments.
Inflow/ Outflow Depth	Accuracy ≤ 2 mm
Inflow/ Outflow Conductivity	Accuracy ≤ 0.05 dS/m
Water Quality	Turbidity ($\pm 2\%$ or ± 0.1 NTU), Temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$), pH (± 0.1), Dissolved Oxygen (± 0.1 mg/l), Nitrogen/ Phosphorus ($\pm 5\%$), heavy metals ($\pm 5\%$) and Hydrocarbons (low $\mu\text{g/L}$).
Precipitation	Accuracy ≤ 0.2 mm

Example layout:

- A: Node w/ rain gauge
- B: Soil Moisture Sensor
- C: CTD in front of headwall

Real-World Example:

Wilberforce Swale, University of Hull

Green Roof

Green roofs help to manage rainfall by reducing runoff, improving water retention, and enhancing urban biodiversity. While all green roofs share these core functions, their design and performance vary depending on factors such as substrate depth, vegetation type, and drainage capacity. Extensive green roofs are lightweight, require minimal maintenance, and typically feature hardy, drought-tolerant vegetation such as sedum, focusing on reducing runoff and providing insulation benefits. In contrast, intensive green roofs have deeper substrates, allowing for a greater variety of plants, including shrubs and small trees, making them more effective for biodiversity and urban cooling but requiring higher maintenance and structural support. Regardless of type, green roofs contribute significantly to stormwater management by absorbing rainfall, slowing runoff, and filtering pollutants before water drains into traditional systems.

Before installation, baseline monitoring is essential to understand existing drainage conditions, particularly the runoff rates from conventional roofs, local rainfall patterns, and the building's structural capacity to support additional weight. This data establishes a reference for assessing the green roof's impact over time. Once installed, ongoing monitoring is necessary to evaluate its effectiveness in reducing runoff, retaining water, and supporting plant growth. Measuring substrate moisture levels ensures optimal conditions for stormwater absorption and vegetation health, while assessing vegetation coverage and biodiversity provides insights into the roof's ecological benefits. Monitoring temperature moderation can also highlight its role in reducing urban heat. Comparing pre- and post-installation data allows for adjustments in design and maintenance, ensuring the green roof continues to deliver both hydrological and environmental benefits. Understanding its performance over time helps refine strategies for maximising its contribution to sustainable urban drainage.

What to monitor:

- **Downpipe flow:** To quantify the input into the planter.
- **Precipitation:** Correlation of rain and water depth/moisture peaks
- **Evapotranspiration (ET):** Indicates rate of water lost from the SuDS

Considerations:

- **Power considerations for nodes:** Battery/Solar panel combination should have sufficient capacity and input to power the whole system, even over long periods of cloudy weather. Replaceable batteries allow continuous monitoring even in the

event of a fault with solar power. Mains power is preferable if it can be facilitated (and planters, due to being located next to buildings, are well suited to this), though this has frequently been found to be difficult.

- **Connectivity with instruments:** Connectivity options should be checked to make sure all equipment can communicate with the central hub. SDI-12 connections have proved successful in our trials, due to being widely available, open, and low power consumption.
- **Overflow system:** To prevent any possible flooding due to blockages of the sensors, an emergency overflow system is recommended to be installed on a planter setup as a failsafe
- **Constriction of flow:** Depending on the pipe configuration/ flow meter selected, water will be required to flow in a downsized pipe. Depending on roof area/ pipe the system may experience backflow. Using the [Drain Calculator](#) web app has the most common pipe sizes to allow for confidence in design.

Suggested Requirements:

Module	Requirements
Node	Solar powered with sufficient battery life or directly wired if possible. Connectivity with all below instruments and capacity for 4 connected instruments.
Outflow	Accuracy: for tipping bucket ≤ 10 ml per tip per m^2 of roof area (equivalent to 0.01mm rain); for constant flow meters ≤ 60 ml $minute^{-1}$ per m^2 . Maximum flow capacity estimated from maximum probable rainfall and roof area.

Example Layout:

Permeable Paving

Permeable paving varies depending on context and design. These systems are also referred to as pervious or porous pavements, with key designs including permeable concrete, block paving, and resin-bound gravel. While the exact functionality of these systems can differ, their overall purpose of reducing surface runoff and promoting infiltration is consistent, and they share similar monitoring requirements. For simplicity, we refer to all systems that allow water to pass through their surface into underlying layers as permeable paving.

Permeable paving systems are designed to capture and temporarily store water in a sub-base layer, facilitating gradual infiltration into the surrounding soil or controlled discharge into drainage systems. These systems can vary in their construction, such as whether they incorporate a geotextile layer or specific filtration media to enhance pollutant removal.

As with other SuDS, monitoring should aim to measure water infiltration rates, surface runoff reduction, and contaminant removal efficiency. Soil moisture and conductivity measurements beneath and around the paving provide critical insights into infiltration performance and the potential movement of contaminants through subsurface layers. Rainfall data and surface runoff monitoring can further help quantify the effectiveness of permeable paving in managing stormwater, as well as its response to varying rainfall intensities and durations.

What to monitor:

- **Outflow Level and Conductivity:** To quantify the flux through the permeable paving and estimate storage and effects on flood peaks.
- **Soil moisture:** Temporal and depth changes in moisture indicate water storage dynamics.
- **Precipitation:** Correlation of rain and water depth/moisture peaks

Considerations:

- **Power considerations for nodes:** Battery/ Solar panel combination should have sufficient capacity and input to power the whole system, even over long periods of cloudy weather. Replaceable batteries allow continuous monitoring even in the event of a fault with solar power. Mains power is preferable if it can be though this has frequently been found to be difficult.
- **Connectivity with instruments:** Connectivity options should be checked to make sure all equipment can communicate with the central hub. SDI-12 connections

have proved successful in our trials, due to being widely available, open, and low power consumption.

- **Installation:** Due to needing to be below a built surface, installation needs to happen at time of construction.

Suggested Requirements:

Module	Requirements
Node	Solar powered with sufficient battery life, or directly wired if possible. Connectivity with all below instruments and capacity for 4 connected instruments.
Chamber level	Accuracy ≤ 2 mm
Chamber conductivity	Accuracy ≤ 0.05 dS/m
Soil Moisture	Length close to soil depth in the permeable paving. Readings at 10 cm intervals or less
Precipitation	Accuracy ≤ 0.2 mm

Example layout:

- A: Node w/ rain gauge
- B: Soil Moisture Sensor
- C: CTD in well behind headwall

Surface Temperature

SuDS are not only essential for managing surface water and improving water quality but also have potential benefits in mitigating the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect. The UHI effect occurs in urban areas where built surfaces, such as roads and buildings, absorb and retain heat, leading to higher temperatures compared to surrounding rural areas. SuDS features, such as green roofs, rain gardens, and permeable paving, can help reduce these temperature differences by incorporating vegetation, increasing evaporation, and reducing heat storage in impervious surfaces.

Using a surface temperature radiometer to monitor SuDS can provide valuable insights into their role in mitigating the UHI effect. A radiometer measures the thermal radiation emitted by a surface, offering precise data on surface temperatures. By comparing the temperatures of SuDS features to traditional urban surfaces like asphalt or concrete, researchers can quantify their cooling effects during different times of the day and seasons.

For example, vegetated SuDS, such as green roofs or bio-swales, often show lower surface temperatures due to shading and evapotranspiration. Permeable paving with light-coloured materials can reflect more sunlight and stay cooler compared to conventional paving. Data from surface temperature radiometers can help assess these effects and guide the design of SuDS to maximise their cooling potential.

Incorporating surface temperature monitoring into SuDS research not only supports better urban planning but also highlights the broader environmental benefits of these systems in creating cooler, more liveable urban spaces.

What to monitor:

- **Surface Temperature:** To quantify surface temperature of targeted surface.

Considerations:

- **Power considerations for nodes:** Battery/ Solar panel combination should have sufficient capacity and input to power the whole system, even over long periods of cloudy weather. Replaceable batteries allow continuous monitoring even in the event of a fault with solar power. Mains power is preferable if it can be facilitated though this has frequently been found to be difficult.
- **Connectivity with instruments:** Connectivity options should be checked to make sure all equipment can communicate with the central hub. SDI-12 connections have proved successful in our trials, due to being widely available, open, and low power consumption.

Suggested Requirements:

Module	Requirements
Node	Solar powered with sufficient battery life, or directly wired if possible. Connectivity with all below instruments and capacity for 3 connected instruments.
Surface Temperature Sensor	Accuracy ≤ 0.2 °C

Example layout:

Real-World Example:

Broadway, Grimsby

Generic Instrumentation

Where novel and innovative solution are used to provide SuDS interventions, some generic guidance can be given for monitoring strategies as described below.

What to monitor:

- **Input-Output comparison:** To quantify the flux through feature, and compare the timing, height and length of discharge peaks from rainfall.
- **Conductivity:** Can be monitored throughout a feature to investigate the effectiveness of the water contaminant remediation.
- **Local precipitation:** Accurate quantification would be especially important for SuDS where the primary input is from precipitation, as in permeable paving or green roofs.
- **Soil moisture:** Important where a large portion of the water storage is within the soil layer, or where the SuDS feature is designed to infiltrate flow to groundwater.
- **Water level:** Important where a large portion of the water is stored as relatively still surface water or within a tank.

Module	Requirements
Node	Solar powered with sufficient battery life or directly wired if possible. Connectivity with all below instruments and capacity for 4 connected instruments.
Water level	Accuracy ≤ 10 mm, or $\leq 1\%$ of depth if depth exceeds 1 m
In/Out flow rate	As above, but with higher accuracies to capture slower flows leaving the planter. for constant flow meters ≤ 5 ml minute ⁻¹ per m ² .
Conductivity	Accuracy ≤ 0.05 dS/m
Soil moisture	Readings at 10 cm intervals, or with sufficient spacing to measure >5 depths throughout the layer of interest, if deeper than 0.5 m. Longer probes may be preferable where the water table is deep below ground, whereas shorter probes with a higher spatial resolution could be used where water tables are shallow.
Precipitation	Accuracy ≤ 0.2 mm

Considerations:

- **Power considerations for nodes:** Battery/ Solar panel combination should have sufficient capacity and input to power the whole system, even over long periods of cloudy weather. Replaceable batteries allow continuous monitoring even in the

event of a fault with solar power. Mains power is preferable if it can be though this has frequently been found to be difficult.

- **Connectivity with instruments:** Connectivity options should be checked to make sure all equipment can communicate with the central hub. SDI-12 connections have proved successful in our trials, due to being widely available, open, and low power consumption.
- **Installation:** Monitoring should be treated during the design phase of works and not an afterthought to allow for infrastructure such as power, conduits and networks to be established.
- **Maintenance:** Some probes/ nodes may require maintenance to keep them operational. Monitoring should be designed to facilitate the easy changing of batteries or cleaning of probes.

Sensor Examples

Function	Equipment	Capability	Indicative Cost (2025)	Comment
Node	Davis Instruments EnviroMonitor Node	In-built solar panel with 1000mAh lithium battery and 4x backup D cells, or directly wired if possible. SDI-12 connection with up to 4 instruments.	£620	
Downpipe/drain flows	Boumatic Pulsameter 2 Tipping bucket gauge	Accuracy 100 ml per tip (equivalent 0.1 mm per tip on a 1 m ² area)	£1200	
Downpipe/drain flows	Tecalemit FMT3 Turbine Flow Meter	Accuracy 2% (1% if calibrated)	£200	
Soil probe	Sentek Drill & Drop probe	Length 15 – 120 cm. Readings at 10 cm intervals. Operates by measuring capacitance.	£1,000	Also determines soil temperature and Volumetric Ion Content (a conductivity proxy)
Water Level	Meter Hydros21 CTD	Accuracy 1mm or 0.25% of depth	£800	
Water conductivity	Integrated in above: Meter Hydros21 CTD	Accuracy ±0.01 dS/m or ±10%, whichever is greater	Incl. in above	
Surface Temperature	SI-421-SS: Research-Grade SDI-12 Digital Output Narrow Field of View Infrared Radiometer Sensor	0.2°C	~£1000	Field of view needs to be accounted for when purchasing.
Precipitation	Separate Davis Aerocone Rain Gauge	0.2 mm per tip	£140	
Precipitation	Davis Vantage Pro2	0.2 mm per tip	£1,200	
Windspeed	Davis Vantage Pro2	Accuracy 2 mph, or 5% rounded if converted to other units	Incl. in above	
Temperature	Davis Vantage Pro2	0.5°F (converted to °C ≈ 0.3)	Incl. in above	
Solar radiation	Davis Vantage Pro2 w/ solar radiation sensor	5%	Incl. in above	Does not meet WMO requirements for solar radiation monitoring, but recommended methodology requires a sun-following mount and glass cover, which would likely make maintenance of multiple stations impractical.

The specific sensor manufacturer and models are provided as examples. Alternative sensors from other manufacturers not listed here are also available. The partners involved in this project do not endorse or recommend any specific manufacturer or model listed within this document, and you should ensure the sensor you choose fits your specific needs prior to installation.

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